

Insights on Mental Health at Work: Impact of Occupational Stress, Happiness and Work Motivation among the Kindergarten Teachers

Anaurene Roy¹ and Nisha Mary George²

Department of Psychology and Counselling, St Joseph's University, Bengaluru, Karnataka¹

Department of Counselling, Mount Carmel PU College, Bengaluru, Karnataka²

This pilot study, conducted on Kindergarten teachers, aimed to investigate the impact of occupational stress, happiness, and work motivation. This ongoing study commenced in 2024, inspired by the theme as given by the World Health Organisation for World Mental Health Day 2024: *Mental Health at Work* (WHO, 2024). 63 kindergarten teachers from Bengaluru participated in the study and completed the Occupational Stress Index-Revised (Srivastava & Singh, 1981), the Subjective Happiness Scale (Lyubomirsky & Lepper, 1999), and the Work Motivation Questionnaire (Agarwal, 1988). A Pearson correlation analysis was adopted to determine the association between the aforementioned variables. The study's findings highlighted that a few dimensions of occupational stress and happiness are inversely associated. Likewise, a few factors of work motivation and a few dimensions of occupational stress were inversely related. The present pilot study highlights the various challenges kindergarten teachers face, which have a profound impact on their motivation to work, happiness, and physical and mental health. Additionally, the recent pandemic has added to the mental turmoil of these teachers, as they had to adopt innovative methods to teach young children effectively during the unanticipated crisis. Overall, this study provides insights into a neglected aspect of teachers' psychological well-being that is affected by occupational challenges.

Keywords: Kindergarten teacher, world mental health day, work motivation, happiness, world health organisation

Mental health concerns have been a top priority for employees across professions. Particularly, in the educational institution, there is a persistent concern that mental health concerns have been ignored. Today, mental health concerns are widely discussed, making it essential to address these issues. Indeed, a conducive environment facilitates better mental health, whereas a non-responsive and unsupportive environment impedes performance, resulting in poor mental health. As a result, in 2024, the World Health Organisation (WHO) centred its mental health activities and awareness programme on the theme '*Mental Health At Work*' (World Health Organisation, 2024). Especially, teaching, which was once considered an easy job, has evolved over time, making it a stressful profession today. Work pressure, excessive workload, lack of psychological safety, and high demands placed by the management of an educational institution are leading to burnout among educators (Corrente, Ferguson, & Bourgeault, 2022; Kun & Gadanez, 2022). The word kindergarten was introduced by Froebel, who exemplified his vision for early childhood education, grounded in the four basic

ideas: free self-expression, creativity, social participation, and motor expression (Zoromski, 2019). These teachers should demonstrate patience, self-motivation, and the ability to connect with young children, which is challenging yet a top priority. Kindergarten teachers' work demands cause job strain as they not only help children to achieve full potential but also contribute to institutional demands. Given the limited research on this specific sample in India, this pilot study offers a valuable and unique perspective on the influence of occupational stress, happiness, and work motivation, aligning with the theme of Mental Health at Work on World Mental Health Day 2024 (WHO, 2024).

Theoretical Framework

Person-environment Fit Theory

The foundational work in contemporary occupational stress research began over three decades ago, primarily using the 'person-environment fit' framework developed by Caplan et al. (1987). This concept refers to the compatibility between individuals and their work environments (Edwards & Shipp, 2007, p. 211). Occupational stress arises mainly in two situations: when the work environment lacks the resources to meet individuals' needs and when individuals' abilities fall short of the demands required to access these resources. Misalignment between a worker's needs or abilities and the demands of the work environment can lead to stress (Caplan, 1987). According to Edward, Caplan, and Harrison (1998), there are three types of misfit: (a) work demands exceed an employee's capabilities, (b) employees' needs are unmet, and (c) both occur simultaneously. Consequently, when educators' professional needs are unmet and their abilities are overstretched, occupational stress can result.

Author Note

¹Anaurene Roy, Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology and Counselling, St Joseph's University, Bengaluru, Karnataka

²Nisha Mary George, Counsellor, Department of Counselling Mount Carmel PU College, Bengaluru, Karnataka
E-mail: nishamary120@gmail.com

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Correspondence concerning this article should be addressed to Anaurene Roy, Assistant Professor, Department of Psychology and Counselling, St Joseph's University, Bengaluru, Karnataka
E-mail: anaurene.roy@sju.edu.in

Performance Happiness Model

Performance and happiness are closely linked and essential for organisational success. Understanding the factors influencing an employee's well-being is crucial (Kun & Gadanez, 2022). Pryce-Jones (2013) notes that an effective performance management system, combined with supportive practices, enhances happiness and boosts organisational outcomes. The performance-happiness model identifies five key dimensions affecting employee satisfaction: (a) Contribution refers to individual performance, (b) Conviction involves short-term motivation, (c) Culture reflects a sense of belonging, (d) Commitment pertains to long-term engagement, and (e) Confidence is the belief in one's ability to perform effectively. These dimensions work together to improve the workplace experience. Happiness is characterised by positive emotions and overall life satisfaction (Diener, 1984). Happy individuals typically have more positive job experiences (Devdutt et al., 2023) and are better able to realise their potential. For instance, in kindergarten, teachers' emotional attachment to students enhances both their job satisfaction and early childhood development (Lomas, Stough, Hansen, & Downey, 2019).

Job Characteristics Model

The job characteristics model by Hackman and Oldham (1980) explores how specific job elements impact job outcomes, such as satisfaction and motivation. The five key characteristics are (a) *skill variety* which refers to the range and complexity of skills required for the job, (b) *task identity* is the extent to which the job is perceived as a complete, standalone task (c) *task significance* reflects the job's impact on the well-being of others (d) *autonomy* indicates the degree of personal initiative permitted in performing the work, (e) *feedback* is the information the job provides regarding performance. The five characteristics can be combined to measure how likely a job is to affect an employee's attitude and behaviour. These characteristics impact three psychological states: the *sense of meaningfulness* (i.e., the perception that the work has a meaningful impact), the *feeling of responsibility for outcomes* (i.e., the degree of accountability the individual feels for their work), and the *awareness of results* (i.e., the awareness of the quality of the individual's performance). When the aforementioned characteristics positively enhance these psychological states, employees can experience increased job satisfaction; however, a deficiency in any of them can lead to decreased job satisfaction (Singh, Singh, Khan, 2016).

Kindergarten teachers, in particular, face higher stress levels as they must balance institutional responsibilities with the need for patience and compassion when working with young children. This role also necessitates maintaining classroom decorum and discipline. Drawing on the theoretical backdrop of person-environment fit, the performance-happiness model, and the job characteristics model, the following section will review relevant literature on occupational stress, happiness, and work motivation.

Research on Occupational Stress, Happiness, and Work Motivation

Occupational stress has six primary causes: job characteristics, individual roles, career development opportunities, working relationships, work-family conflict and organisational structure (Lu, Cooper, Kao, & Zhou, 2003). Antoniou, Davidson, and Cooper (2006) effectively categorise sources of stress into exogenous

factors, such as working conditions and workload, and endogenous factors, including individual personality traits. Loo, Amin, and Rahman (2015) emphasise that factors such as work-life imbalance, excessive workloads, poor working conditions, low salaries, and inadequate communication significantly contribute to ongoing stress among social workers. A study investigated the long-term effects of role stressors, specifically role overload and role ambiguity, on psychological strain among academics at public universities in Malaysia. The analysis revealed that role overload and role ambiguity are predictors of psychological strain over time, whereas role conflict is not (Idris, 2008). Among the many studies on teachers, a few focused predominantly on kindergarten teachers in India. In a study examining work-related stress and its relationship with gender, age, years of experience, and highest degree obtained, the findings indicated that teachers with higher qualifications experienced higher stress levels than those with lower qualifications. Likewise, a strong association was found between stress and several factors mentioned above (Agai-Demjaha, Bislimovska, & Mijakoski, 2015). Absenteeism, rapid career transitions, and a lack of career commitment were commonly reported among teachers experiencing high stress and low job satisfaction. With the COVID-19 lockdown in place, new teaching demands and heavy schedules have been added to the existing stressors (Keleynikov, Benatov, & Berger, 2022). With over 200 countries suspending schools and kindergartens due to the COVID-19 outbreak, which has affected millions of students globally (Verksa et al., 2021) a remote learning model was immediately implemented to maintain the continuity of education for children. A recent study involving 909 pre-school educators (623 from Russia & 286 from India) found that cultural factors significantly influenced perception of distance education. India, with its diverse culture, is found to have teachers who are more flexible and exhibit a more positive attitude than their Russian counterparts (Verksa et al., 2021). Another study examined the demographic variables, i.e., gender, age, salary, and work experience, that affect occupational stress and job satisfaction. The results revealed a negative correlation between occupational stress and job satisfaction due to factors such as the absence of physical proximity, limited face-to-face interaction, reduced engagement in activities, and a lack of hands-on experience during kindergarten training (Balamurugan, Herbert, Rajakrishnan, & Dhanasekar, 2022). In a few recent studies conducted around the pandemic, similar results were reported (Keleynikov et al., 2022; Onyeaka et al., 2021).

Undoubtedly, employees experience happiness and job satisfaction when their working environment is perceived as conducive (Benevene et al., 2019; Seligman, 2011; Kosasih & Basit, 2019). Teaching is no exception from the same. A teacher must be able to integrate educational practices with extracurricular activities to demonstrate effective, creative teaching that engages students, especially young children. Over the past few decades, significant research has been conducted on workplace happiness. For instance, Yadav's (2012) study aimed to explore the relationship between happiness and teaching effectiveness among teachers across primary-intermediate levels. The results indicated a positive association between the two variables, particularly among high school and intermediate teachers. Another study by Tadic, Bakker, and Oerlemans (2013) found that self-concordant motivation reduced the negative impact of work demands on happiness among 132 teachers teaching in an institution. Recently, Pan, Fan, Wang,

and Li (2022) investigated the relationship between mindfulness and the subjective well-being of 323 kindergarten teachers in China. The findings suggested a significant, direct relationship between mindfulness and subjective well-being. Higher levels of mindfulness are associated with increased feelings of happiness and life satisfaction among teachers. A major challenge kindergarten teachers faced during the COVID-19 pandemic was that Organisations and employees depend on each other to achieve their goals (Chanana & Sangeeta, 2020). Recently, a research article examined whether kindergarten teachers made career transitions or permanently left teaching due to stress, exhaustion, burnout, and technological influences. Using a phenomenological research approach, the data were collated using three methods: semi-structured interviews, group activities, and member-checking interviews with 60 kindergarten teachers. The findings emphasise that personal factors, including family considerations, professional skills, the surrounding environment, and financial factors, significantly influence their career decisions and sources of stress (Santos, 2021). Using a two-way longitudinal design, a recent study assessed the influence of the longitudinal relationship between 782 kindergarten teachers and children in Hong Kong on psychological well-being, self-efficacy, and commitment. A half-longitudinal mediation analysis reveals that commitment has improved teachers' psychological well-being through self-efficacy over time (Yin, Tom, & Lau, 2023).

As the number of working married couples continues to rise, there has been a significant shift in the approach to infant and child care. This transition is driven by the demands of modern lifestyles. Motivation plays a vital role in teachers' effectiveness and satisfaction in their profession. Recognising their role can help foster a more positive and productive educational environment for educators and students. A study of 1169 Romanian teachers (i.e., 501 teachers from kindergarten & 668 teachers from primary schools) found a strong link between intrinsic and extrinsic motivation for extracurricular activities. Additionally, headaches and difficulty concentrating were attributed to stress and pressure among teachers (Masari, Muntele, & Curelaru, 2013). Similarly, another study aims to explore how the motivation and knowledge of 80 kindergarten teachers significantly impact their organisational citizenship behaviour in Bogor City. A partial t-test and multilinear regression revealed that teachers' knowledge and motivation influence organisational citizenship behaviour (Laihad & Suhardi, 2023). The COVID-19 pandemic posed a serious threat to teachers' motivation in the workplace due to online learning and the use of digital tools for teaching, thereby undermining their commitment and enthusiasm for educating students (Adarkwah, 2023). A few studies have comprehensively examined teachers' work motivation during the pandemic. A survey of 5783 kindergarten teachers in China examines occupational commitment and its influencing factors during the COVID-19 pandemic. The findings reveal that kindergarten teachers have generally shown positive job commitment, even during the COVID-19 pandemic. Specifically, affective and normative commitments were satisfactory, whereas continuance commitment required enhancement (Meyer, Stanley, Herscovitch, & Topolnytsky, 2002). Teachers' occupational commitment in kindergarten schools owned by the National Ministry of Education was significantly higher than that of their counterparts in private institutions. Additionally, the commitment levels of permanent kindergarten teachers were notably higher than those of contract teachers. Income

reduction emerged as a prevalent issue during the pandemic, particularly affecting teachers on contract and was significantly negatively correlated with occupational commitment (Wei, Wang, Li, & Zhou, 2021).

In India, where demand for quality education continues to rise, there is a need to address the often-overlooked stress levels of teachers, especially those in kindergarten schools. In the past, research in psychology has explored many aspects of human behaviour. The existing literature primarily focuses on occupational stress and its relationship with happiness and work motivation among primary and/or secondary school teachers. Following the COVID-19 pandemic, some studies have reported similar findings and new insights related to the challenges of technology-based learning. On the basis of the aforementioned literature, the current study aims to explore the relationship between occupational stress, happiness, and work motivation, specifically among kindergarten teachers, in alignment with the current global theme of Mental Health at Work by WHO.

Method

Participants

The participants recruited for the study are female kindergarten teachers. A total of 54 kindergarten schools were contacted in Bengaluru city, of which 38 schools agreed to participate in the study. There were 63 responses obtained from the contacted schools. However, those participants did not meet the inclusion criteria of the Montessori diploma training qualification (National Child Development Council, 2024), which is as per the Indian education system. Those questionnaires with missing responses were excluded from the study. Thus, the final sample consisted of 50 female kindergarten teachers ($M = 25.50$, $SD = 14.58$). The age range of the selected participants is between 21-40 years ($M_{age} = 33.76$, $SD = 4.49$). Subsequently, to gather data, a background survey on educational qualifications, work experience, place of residence, and other relevant factors is administered to the participants. To explore the relationships among occupational stress, happiness, and work motivation, a correlational research design is used to provide a comprehensive understanding of their interactions.

Measures

Occupational Stress Index-Revised (OSI-R). This scale was developed by Srivastava and Singh (1981) to assess employees' occupational stress levels. In the present study, OSI-R is administered to kindergarten teachers. The OSI-R aims to assess employees' perceived stress due to various aspects of their job roles, and is applicable to all levels across industries, particularly supervisory positions and above. The questionnaire consists of 46 statements and 12 dimensions. The following are the dimensions in this scale with an example of each; (a) *role overload* (an example for this dimension is 'I have to do a lot of work in this job'), (b) *role ambiguity* (for instance is 'The objectives of my work role are quite clear & adequately planned), an example for (c) *role conflict* is 'It becomes difficult to implement all of a sudden the new dealing procedures and policies in place of those already in practice'. An example of (d) *unreasonable group and political pressure* is "I have to do some work unwillingly owing to certain group/political pressures; (e) *responsibility for persons* (for example, 'I bear the great responsibility for the progress & prosperity of this

organisation'), (f) *under participation* (e.g., 'Most of my suggestions are heeded and implemented here'), an item to measure (g) *powerlessness* is 'My suggestion regarding the training programmes of the employees are given due significance'. An example of (h) *poor peer relations* is 'I have to work with persons whom I like'. An example of (i) *intrinsic impoverishment* is 'My assignments are monotonous in nature', and (j) *low status*, for example, is 'My higher authorities do not give due significance to my post'. An example of (k) *strenuous working conditions* is 'I often feel that this job has made my life cumbersome', and finally, an item to measure (l) *unprofitability* is 'I am seldom rewarded for my hard labour and efficient performance. The items were rated on a five-point Likert scale (1 = *strongly agree* & 5 = *strongly disagree*). A few items (i.e., 18 items) on the scale were scored reversely (for example, 5 = *strongly agree* & 1 = *strongly disagree*). The scale has established good psychometric properties. In the split-half method, the reliability index was .93, and Cronbach's alpha was .90 (Latif & Sultana, 2011).

Subjective Happiness Scale (SHS): The Subjective Happiness Scale, developed by Lyubomirsky and Lepper (1999) assesses an individual's overall happiness and captures a broader understanding of well-being. This scale includes four items, each measured on a seven-point Likert scale. In the first two items, participants must assess their overall happiness (1 = *not very happy*, 7 = *very happy*) and their peers' happiness (1 = *less happy*, 7 = *more happy*). The other two items generally describe how happy and unhappy the individuals are, and the participants indicate how well each description aligns with their experience (1 = *not at all* to 7 = *a great deal*). This scale also established good psychometric properties. The reliability test was .55 to .90, and the validity was .52 to .72.

Work Motivation Questionnaire (WMQ). The WMQ is a dynamic psychological process that energises and sustains action, reflecting an intrinsic drive to exert effort. It integrates biological, emotional, social, and cognitive forces influencing behaviour. Individuals, including kindergarten teachers, are motivated when they anticipate that a particular course of action will likely result in attaining meaningful goals and rewards that fulfil their needs and desires. This questionnaire, developed by Agarwal (1988) includes 26 items across six factors: The following are the six factors (a) *dependence* (e.g., 'How often does your immediate superior talk to you in an appreciative/ encouraging way?'), (b) *organisational orientation* (e.g., 'All in all, how satisfied are you with your job?'), (c) *work group relations* (for instance, 'How do you like the kind of work you do in your organisation?'), (d) *psychological work incentives* (e.g., 'To what extent do you feel that you are doing useful work here?'). An example of (e) *material incentives* is 'How satisfied do you feel about your chances of promotion in your organisation?' (f) *job situation* (e.g., 'To what extent does your job give you a chance to use your best abilities to do things you are best at?'). The items were assessed using a five-point Likert scale (5 = *most positive response*; 1 = *extreme negative response*), yielding valuable insights into participants' perspectives. By the split-half method, the reliability coefficient was found to be .99.

Procedure and Data Analysis

After obtaining ethical approval from the St Joseph's Research and Innovation Council at St Joseph's University, the participants were informed of the study's purpose. They provided their consent before completing the questionnaires. The demographic information of the participants, including name (optional), age, gender, years of

experience, qualifications, and other relevant details, was provided along with the questionnaires, that is, the OSIR, SHS, and WMQ. Using a paper-and-pencil method, all the data were collected, then entered into an Excel spreadsheet and analysed using SPSS version 27. To examine the relationships among occupational stress, happiness, and work motivation in female kindergarten teachers, descriptive statistics, including the mean and standard deviation, and a Pearson correlation coefficient were used.

Results and Discussion

In line with the theme of mental health in the workplace, this pilot study examines whether occupational stress influences happiness and work motivation among kindergarten teachers in India. For strengthening our understanding of this issue, insights from participants were gathered.

The following results are based on the proposed theoretical backdrop of the person-environment fit theory (see Caplan, 1987), the performance-happiness model (see Pryce-Jones, 2013), and the job characteristics model (see Hackman & Oldham, 1980). Descriptive statistics highlight a mean score ranging from $M = 14.64, SD = 2.70$ to $M = 5.56, SD = 2.04$ across the 12 dimensions of the OSI-R. The mean score in the SHS is $M = 5.17, SD = .86$. Likewise, the results in the WMQ range from $M = 22.28, SD = 2.71$ to $M = 12.72, SD = 1.55$ across six dimensions. All dimensions in the OSI-R, SHS, and WMQ are normally distributed, as evidenced by skewness and kurtosis within acceptable ranges for psychometric properties (Field, 2010).

Table 1

Pearson Correlation Results between Occupational Stress and Happiness

	Happiness
Role overload	-.18
Role ambiguity	-.194
Role conflict	-.386**
Unreasonable group and political pressure	-.122
Responsibility for persons	-.041
Under participation	-.389**
Powerlessness	.279*
Poor peer relations	.119
Intrinsic impoverishment	-.193
Low status	.081
Strenuous working conditions	-.187
Unprofitability	-.181

Following the aforementioned preliminary analysis, Pearson product-moment correlation method analyses how the dimensions influence one another. Correlations observed between occupational stress, subjective happiness and work motivation are illustrated in Tables 1 and 2. The results signify there is a positive yet small relationship between powerlessness and happiness, while there is a low inverse correlation between role conflict, under-participation, and happiness. However, no statistical relationship is found between the other nine dimensions of the OSI-R and SHS. Similarly, the relationship observed between the dimensions of WMQ and the OSI-R reveals important insights into how work motivation is influenced by occupational stress among kindergarten teachers. The analysis highlights a low to moderate correlation range between the WMQ and OSI-R dimensions. A positive association is found

between dependence on powerlessness and low status, while an inverse correlation is observed between dependence on role overload

and unreasonable group and political pressure. There was no association found with the remaining eight dimensions of OSI-R.

Table 2

Pearson Correlation Results between Occupational Stress and the Factors of Work Motivation

	Factor 1 dependence	Factor 2 organizational orientation	Factor 3 work group relations	Factor 4 psychological work incentives	Factor 5 material incentives	Factor 6 job situation
Role overload	-.412**	-.322*	-.425**	-.207	-.361**	-.302**
Role ambiguity	-.04	.076	-.23	-.556**	-.381**	-.26**
Role conflict	-.228	-.532**	-.294*	.06	-.550**	-.369**
Unreasonable group and political pressure	-.502**	-.320*	-.494**	-.529**	-.319**	-.308**
Responsibility for persons	-.265	-.334*	-.179	.164	-.173**	-.055
Under participation	.136	.015	.11	.04	-.051**	.026
Powerlessness	.412**	.418**	.424**	.264	.500**	.388**
Poor peer relations	.042	.353*	-.26	-.146	.073**	-.355*
Intrinsic impoverishment	-.133	-.194	-.07	-.27	-.398**	.059
Low status	.351*	-.099	.333*	.05	-.340*	-.032
Strenuous working conditions	-.136	-.096	-.275	-.411**	-.488**	-.142
Unprofitability	-.022	-.337*	.054	-.051	-.409**	-.104

Note. significant at .05

In the context of organisational orientation, there is a positive relationship between feelings of powerlessness and poor peer relations. Conversely, an inverse relationship exists concerning role overload, role conflict, unprofitability, responsibility for others, as well as unreasonable group dynamics and political pressures. No relationship was identified with the other five dimensions of the OSI-R. Workgroup relations correlate positively with powerlessness and low status while showing an inverse relationship with role overload, role conflict, unreasonable groups and political pressure. Additionally, other WMQ dimensions do not correlate with these factors. Furthermore, psychological work incentives demonstrated a moderate inverse relationship with strenuous working conditions, unreasonable groups, and political pressure. There is, however, no statistically significant relationship with the other 10 dimensions of OSI-R. Only powerlessness is positively correlated with material incentives. Role overload, role conflict, intrinsic impoverishment, low status, strenuous working conditions, unreasonable groups and political pressure negatively correlated with material incentives. Subsequent scale dimensions did not show any relationship with the aforementioned factor. Powerlessness is the only dimension in the OSI-R that is positively correlated with the dimensions of job situations in the WMQ. On the contrary, role overload, role conflict, poor peer relations, unreasonable groups and political pressure are inversely related to job situations. Furthermore, no relationship is found between the remaining dimensions of OSI-Rs and the job situation in WMQ.

In an institution, individuals typically remain engaged in their assigned tasks, regardless of whether they are intrinsically or extrinsically motivated (Masari et al., 2013). Additionally, many professionals within these institutions feel powerless. The study's findings reveal that kindergarten teachers also share this feeling of powerlessness. Kindergarten teachers may face emotional pressures that affect their decisions, given the delicate nature of working with

children, and are compelled to work beyond their job designation (Kwong, 2016). During COVID-19, this stress was perhaps doubled as teachers had to equip themselves with the latest technological tools for teaching (Keleynikov et al., 2022). Along with numerous deadlines and responsibilities in the teaching profession, the workload has become increasingly stressful, affecting their physical and mental health. Fostering a relaxed atmosphere and positive environment will enhance their enthusiasm and job satisfaction. Kindergarten teachers' well-being directly impacts the quality of young children's education (Santos, 2021). Teachers' involvement in effective decision-making is crucial for institutions. When they are involved in the decisionmaking process, it enhances their job satisfaction, commitment, motivation, and happiness (Yin et al., 2023).

In contrast, limiting their decision-making can decrease their happiness by diminishing their connection to the institution (Keung, 2008). Despite the challenges of powerlessness, teachers experience job satisfaction and fulfilment in their work environment, thus contributing to happiness (Kwong, 2016). An optimal level of job demands encourages individuals to engage in challenging tasks. In any institution, individuals sometimes discover that their roles deviate from their job descriptions as they evolve with experience and needs (e.g., social worker, motivator, & counsellor). This can result in feeling overwhelmed, especially when handling tasks for which they lack training, for instance, the introduction of sudden online classes during COVID-19 (Keleynikov et al., 2022; Onyeaka et al., 2022; Adarkwah, 2023). When demands exceed and contradict an individual's expectations, it creates interpersonal and intrapersonal conflicts. The stress caused by role conflicts negatively impacts their well-being and reduces happiness. Idris (2011) also found that unreasonable expectations can lead to role conflict, which can negatively affect happiness. Similarly, a lack of extrinsic motivators can also decrease the level of happiness among

kindergarten teachers (Lee et al., 2014). Teachers often experience low status due to a lack of power, money, and recognition. Despite their training and influence, this contributes to reduced workplace happiness, as noted in a study by Hall and Langton (2006).

In the Indian system, where teaching is considered a respected profession, it is essential to prioritise kindergarten teachers' well-being and development. With well-defined responsibilities, supportive management, and a team that fosters greater inclusivity and appreciation, it is quite natural to see an increase in psychological well-being (Pan et al., 2022; Benevene et al., 2019). These motivators enable and encourage teachers to be more loyal to the institution (Toorn et al., 2014). Teachers are more willing to contribute when such positive contingencies are attached, which can facilitate meaningful connections between teachers and students, especially during early childhood. Conversely, inadequate support, challenging leadership styles, and a lack of trust in management can impede teachers' professional development, leading to reduced performance and increased mental and physical strain (Christophersen et al., 2015). The situation worsened with the global COVID-19 pandemic, which affected all sectors of the economy, including the education system. The abrupt implementation of remote education challenged the effectiveness of teaching, particularly in delivering lessons and activities to all students. Teachers had to teach young children using innovative methods to engage students and habituate them to traditional learning methods. For this, the teachers had to undergo training on various online tools and software to deliver the syllabus prescribed to students (see Adarkwah, 2023). Nevertheless, despite such facilities, many teachers struggled to manage students' active participation during online classes and often had to cope with distractions at home. In some educational institutions, management failed to compensate for this teaching and often demanded that students handle challenges and tasks in the offline mode. The lack of flexibility and perhaps poor technological disabilities led to physical and mental strain in the workplace. The aforementioned findings indicate that unrealistic expectations, conflicting demands, and unclear responsibilities contribute to stress, thus reducing motivation.

Conclusion and Limitations of the Study

In summary, the present study provides insight into how happiness and work motivation are influenced by factors that affect an individual's work-related stress levels. This year, WHO's theme emphasises the need to address mental health and well-being in the workplace to safeguard employees' health and well-being and enhance overall organisational/institutional effectiveness. Considering the level of stress, happiness, and motivation experienced by kindergarten teachers, the findings suggest that as the complexities and demands of their roles and responsibilities rise, it can lead to mental health issues. Especially when there is an increasing lack of sufficient instructions, guidance, and orientation specific to the nature of their job. Likewise, low pay, lack of support, and other such factors can further exacerbate the challenges they face, potentially impacting their overall well-being and classroom effectiveness. The COVID-19 restrictions were no exception. It further intensified the demand for immediate attention and action within a short period. It forced the teachers to upskill in new technologies and online teaching methods that resembled traditional classroom instruction. Teaching is a stressful job, and the COVID-19 lockdown created uncertainties across all sectors, including

educational outcomes for students and employees' return to work in the institution, worsening the situation further. The setbacks the teachers have encountered have had a notable effect on their mental well-being, prompting reflection on their professional satisfaction and performance. The primary limitation of this study is its small sample size. Thus, further research should focus on a large sample size that could substantiate the present results and identify the impact of occupational stress on happiness and work motivation. Another limitation of the pilot study is that the sample is restricted to a particular metropolitan and cosmopolitan city in South India. The responses were collected using a scale developed specifically for the Indian population, which means the findings were analysed within the context of the Indian education system. Despite inevitable challenges, kindergarten teachers continue to support and guide young children's development.

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